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Study of the Pathogenicity of *Moniliophthora* Spp. Isolates From Branches of Kola Trees (*Cola Nitida* (Vent.) Scott & Endl.) Infected With Witches' Broom Disease

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Abstract

The main objective was to study in the greenhouse the pathogenicity of six isolates of *Moniliophthora* spp. on kola trees. To achieve this objective, branches of kola trees bearing the symptoms of the disease were collected in the main kola nut production areas (Danane, Meagui, Daloa, Agboville, Abengourou and Aboisso) and at the CNRA research station in Divo. The necrotic (dry brooms) and non-necrotic (green brooms) parts were disinfected and then placed on agar water (1.5% gelatin). Six isolates of *Moniliophthora* spp. were obtained after one week of incubation. The morphological characteristics of these isolates were studied on PDA medium and carrot medium. Thus, all the *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates studied were able to grow on both culture media. However, the carrot organic medium allowed good mycelial growth. For the identification of the causal agent of the disease, a pathogenicity test was set up and a fully randomised experimental design with seven treatments repeated three times was used. The factor studied was the *Moniliophthora* spp. isolate with six modalities. The experimental unit consisted of 10 plants, all six months old. The variables measured were the latency period of the isolates, their virulence and their aggressiveness. Results showed that all isolates caused disease symptoms in inoculated plants while uninoculated plants were apparently healthy. The first symptoms appeared after one week for isolates KOCIV 1-1, KOCIV 1-2, KOCIV 1-3 and KOCIV 1-4. Isolates KOCIV 1-5 and KOCIV 1-6 showed symptoms after two weeks. The KOCIV 1-4 isolate was the most virulent with a virulence rate of 59% and the KOCIV 1-6 isolate was the least virulent with a virulence rate of 33%. In the future, a molecular identification of the isolates is necessary to better understand the pathogen in order to select resistant plant material.

Keywords : Witches' broom, Kola tree, *Moniliophthora* spp., pathogen, virulence.

1. INTRODUCTION

kola tree is cultivated for the kola nut, which is highly prized worldwide and in Africa for its socio-cultural and industrial uses (Yahaya et al. 2002; Asogwa et al. 2006). Also, the kola nut is a nerve stimulant and heart tonic. In Cote d'Ivoire, the species cultivated is *Cola nitida*. The nuts of this species are the most appreciated in the sub-region and in the world (CNRA, 2002). Cote d'Ivoire is the world's leading producer of kola nuts, ahead of Nigeria, with an estimated production of 260,000 t/year of fresh nuts, generating a turnover of more than CFA 78 billion (MINADER, 2018).

Despite its socio-economic importance, kola nut production faces several difficulties. These include the lack of efficient planting material, slow germination of kola nuts (Mbeté et al., 2011), farmers' difficulties in accessing technical assistance (Kama, 2009), pest attacks and witches' broom disease (Kama, 2009; Gbedie et al., 2019).

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The latter is the main disease of the kola tree (Gbedie et al., 2019). Indeed, it attacks both the juvenile and adult stages of the cola tree (Gbedie et al., 2019). The symptoms of the disease are mainly manifested by an abnormal proliferation of buds leading to a swelling of the shoots, with excessive branching, and a shortening of the internodes, giving them a characteristic "broom" appearance. It can cause production losses of up to 60% in the absence of phytosanitary measures (Gbedie et al., 2019).

Indeed, the pathogen responsible for this disease has not yet been identified, let alone its pathogenicity studied. Thus, the present study was conducted to characterise six isolates of *Moniliophthora* spp. collected from branches of kola trees bearing the symptoms of the disease in the major kola nut production zones (Danane, Meagui, Daloa, Agboville, Abengourou and Aboisso) and at the CNRA research station in Divo, and to study their pathogenicity in the greenhouse on six-month-old kola tree.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. MATERIALS

2.1.1. Plant material

The plant material used consisted of 210 plants from nuts collected from a kola plot at the CNRA research station in Divo (CNRA) (5°50'27.8"N, 5°21'30.1"W) in Cote d'Ivoire. The plot consisted of several 12-year-old genotypes.

2.1.2. Fungal material

The fungal material used for the pathogenicity test consisted of six isolates (KOCIV 1-1, KOCIV 1-2, KOCIV 1-3, KOCIV 1-4, KOCIV 1-5 and KOCIV 1-6) of *Moniliophthora* spp. obtained from kola trees branches bearing symptoms of witches' broom disease collected from plots in Danane, Daloa, Meagui, Agboville, Abengourou, Aboisso and from the CNRA research station in Divo.

2.1.3. Culture media

Two culture media were studied during this work. These were the PDA medium (Potato Dextrose Agar) and the MC medium (Carrot medium).

2.2 METHODS

2.2.1. Preparation of culture media

2.2.2.1 Carrot culture medium

For the preparation of this medium, a total of 200 g of fresh carrots were weighed, rinsed and boiled in 500 ml of distilled water for 45 min, and simmered for 25 min. The carrots were then ground in a blender and filtered. The resulting filtrate was made up to 1000 ml with distilled water. To 400 ml of the diluted filtrate, 8 g of agar was added. The resulting solution in an Erlenmeyer flask was hermetically sealed with carded cotton and kraft paper. Following this, the solution was autoclaved at 121°C, under 1bar pressure for 20 min. Finally, after sterilisation, the medium was poured under a laminar flow hood, near a Bunsen burner flame, into 90 mm Petri dishes.

2.2.2.2 PDA culture medium

For the preparation of this medium, 10 g of potato powder was measured and boiled in 500 ml of distilled water for 20 min, and simmered for 25 min. The contents were filtered using filter paper and cotton wool. The filtrate obtained was made up to 500 ml to which 5 g of glucose and 10 g of agar were added. 100 ml of the agar medium was taken and introduced into the roux vials. The vials containing the PDA medium were autoclaved for 30 min for sterilisation and then spread over the domed surface of each roux vial.

2.2.2. Isolation and purification of fungal isolates

For each collection zone, branches with dry broom (necrotic parts) and green broom (non-necrotic parts) symptoms were disinfected with 95% alcohol and then flamed for 30 seconds. The sampling area at the periphery of the necrotic and non-necrotic parts was selected and the superficial tissues were stripped with a sterile scalpel. Three fragments of 6 mm cubic each were removed from the subcortical tissue with a sterile punch. These fragments were placed on a water agar medium (1.5% gelatin) autoclaved at 121°C for 30 minutes and poured into 90 mm diameter petri dishes. After seven days of incubation in the dark in an oven, the isolates obtained were purified by successive subculturing on PDA medium contained in petri dishes. The isolates were transferred by sampling at the growth front of an agar fragment, containing very fine mycelial filaments.

2.2.3. Inoculum Production

Each isolate fragment was transplanted into the roux vials, on solidified PDA medium, at a rate of six vials per isolate. The roux vials, covered with a black tarpaulin, were then incubated in a chamber at a temperature of 26°C for seven days with a 12-hour light and 12-hour dark cycle. After the seven days, the black tarpaulin were removed and the roux vials were kept in the incubation chamber with the same alternating light for a period of two weeks. This technique favoured sporulation of the isolates. The liquid inoculum was obtained by adding 5 ml of sterile distilled water to each vial, which was then left to stand for 10 minutes. Each vial was then homogenised and, using a sterile Pasteur pipette, the surface of the PDA solid medium culture was gently scraped off. The resulting spore suspension was calibrated with a Malassez cell to a concentration of 6.10^5 spores/ml using the following formula :

$$C = \left(\frac{N}{a.v} \right) * Fd$$

With N = Number of spores counted; a = Number of counting units counted; v = Volume of a counting unit and Fd = Number of dilutions.

2.2.4 Plants Obtaining

Fresh nuts from the kola plots of the CNRA were harvested and stored in transparent plastic bags. They were scarified, soaked in water for 24 hours and sown in a germoir. One month after sowing, the plants from the pre-germinated nuts were transplanted into black plastic bags perforated at the base, 30 cm long and 15 cm in diameter, containing potting soil. The plants were watered every other day with tap water until the inoculation stage (six months).

2.2.5. Plants inoculation

The six-month-old plants, placed in trays, were preconditioned in an incubation chamber at 26°C and sprayed with distilled water for 24 hours. This preconditioning allowed a relative humidity close to saturation to be maintained. For each isolate, 30 plants were inoculated. The spore suspension was sprayed on all parts of the plants at a rate of 20 ml of solution per plant. The control plants received a quantity of sterile distilled water equivalent to the quantity of inoculum (20 ml). After inoculation, the plants were placed in an incubation chamber in the dark for two days at 26°C.

2.2.5 Experimental design

After incubation, the 30 inoculated plants per isolate and the non-inoculated (control plants) were brought to the greenhouse and then distributed according to a completely randomised design with three replications. The factor studied was the *Moniliophthora* spp. isolate with seven modalities: the control inoculated with sterile distilled water (T_0), isolates KOCIV1-1 (T_1), KOCIV 1-2 (T_2), KOCIV 1-3 (T_3), KOCIV 1-4 (T_4), KOCIV 1-5 (T_5) and KOCIV 1-6 (T_6). Each experimental unit consisted of 10 plants placed in trays measuring 1.67 m x 1.50 m and covered with transparent plastic film. This arrangement made it possible to maintain a high relative humidity favourable to germination and conidial development and to avoid contamination between the different treatments. The plants were arranged in rows with a spacing of 5 cm

between rows and between plants. The plants were watered with sterile distilled water three times a day to maintain a relative humidity close to saturation.

2.2.7 Measured variables

- Mycelial growth speed

On each culture medium and for each isolate, the estimation of mycelial growth consisted of measuring the radial growth of the pathogen colonies six days after seeding (DAS) using a graduated ruler. The measured radial growth (mm) was divided by the number of days after seeding (d). The radial growth rate of the mycelium of each *Moniliophthora* spp. isolate was calculated by the following formula :

$$\text{Growth speed} = \left(\frac{\text{radial growth (mm)}}{\text{Number of observation days (j)}} \right)$$

- Latency period

The latency period is the time (days) between inoculation and the appearance of the first symptoms.

- Isolates virulence

The virulence of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates was measured by the number of diseased plants in relation to the total number of inoculated plants. It was calculated according to the following formula :

$$\text{Virulence rate (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of diseased plants}}{\text{Total number of inoculated plants}} \right) * 100$$

- Isolates Aggressiveness

The aggressiveness of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates was measured from the number of axillary brooms per plant. It was calculated from the following formula :

$$\text{Aggressiveness rate (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Total number of axillary brooms per plant}}{\text{Total number of observed plants}} \right) * 100$$

2.2.8 Statistical analysis

The normality of the data was verified by the Shapiro-Wilk test at the 5% threshold (Shapiro and Wilk, 1965). All data collected were analysed using STATISTICA 7.1 software. For the parameters examined, a comparison of the means between the different factors and treatments was done through simple analysis of variance (ANOVA). When a significant difference is observed between the treatments for a given factor, the ANOVA is completed by post-hoc tests using the Newman-Keuls test at the 5% probability threshold. This test identifies the treatment whose effect differs significantly from the other treatments for the chosen factor.

3. RESULTS

3.1.Characteristics of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates

3.1.1. Effect of culture medium and *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates on the radial growth of mycelium.

The effect of the "Culture medium x Isolate" interaction was highly significant on the radial growth rate of the mycelium ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1). No significant difference was observed between the culture media studied ($p = 0.259$).

Table I : Effect of culture medium, isolate and their interaction on the radial growth rate of isolates.

SS	DF	MS	F	p
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Culture media	0,47	1	0,47	1,28	0,259874
Isolates	358,90	5	71,78	194,50	< 0.001
Culture*Isolates	65,86	5	13,17	35,69	< 0.001
Error	35,43	96	0,37		

SS : Sum of Squares ; DF : Degree of Freedom ; MS : Mean of Squares ; F : Fischer ; p : Probability.

Isolates KOCIV 1-2 and KOCIV 1-3, with mycelial growths of 76.1 mm and 69.9 mm respectively, grew well on the PDA medium. Isolates KOCIV 1-1 and KOCIV 1-6 grew best on carrot medium with mycelial growths of 85 mm and 83 mm respectively. Isolate KOCIV 1-4 had a mycelial growth of 47.8 mm and 46 mm on PDA and carrot media respectively. Isolate KOCIV 1-5 had a mycelial growth of 73.8 mm and 75 mm on PDA and Carrot media respectively (Figure 1).

* Data with the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level according to the Newman-Keuls test; MC and PDA

Figure 1 : Radial growth of mycelium of 6 isolates of *Moniliophthora* spp. on PDA and MC media

3.2. Assessment of the pathogenicity of *Moniliophthora* spp.

3.2.1. Latency period according to *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates

Analysis of variance showed a significant difference in the latency of the *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates studied (Table II). The isolates KOCIV 1-1, KOCIV 1-2, KOCIV 1-3 and KOCIV 1-4 caused the appearance of symptoms in inoculated plants one week after inoculation. In contrast, symptoms did not appear until day 14 with isolates KOCIV 1-5 and KOCIV 1-6.

Table II : Latency period according to *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates

	SS	DF	MS	F	p
Latency	36,0	1	36,0	34,9	< 0.001
Error	16,5	16	1,0		

SC : Sum of Squares ; DF : Degree of Freedom ; MS : Mean of Squares ;

F : Fischer ; p : Probability.

3.2.2. Assessment of the virulence of *Moniliophthora* spp.

The analysis of variance presented in Table III revealed a highly significant difference between treatments for the rate of diseased plants ($p < 0.001$). One month after inoculation, this rate varied between 33% and 59% (Figure 2). The KOCIV 1-4 isolate was more virulent than the other isolates with a virulence rate of 59%. Isolates KOCIV 1-6, KOCIV 1-1, KOCIV 1-3, KOCIV 1-5 and KOCIV 1-2 were less virulent with a

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virulence rate that varied from 33% to 47%. Control plants sprayed with distilled water were free of disease. Figure 3 shows the symptoms of witches' broom disease on kola trees.

Table III : Analysis of variance of the factor "Isolates" on the number of diseased plants.

	SS	DF	MS	F	p
Isolates	6,03761	6	1,00627	4,7160	< 0.001
Error	43,10115	202	0,21337		

SS : Sum of Squares ; DF : Degree of Freedom ; MC : Mean of Squares ;

F : Fischer ; p : Probability.

* Data with the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level according to the Newman-Keuls test.

Figure 2 : Virulence rate of isolates on infected plants

Figure 3 : Symptoms of witches' broom disease at the level of the apex and axillary buds on plants inoculated in the greenhouse.

3.2.3. Assessment of the aggressiveness of *Moniliophthora* spp.

The aggressiveness of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates was measured in relation to the average number of axillary brooms on each diseased plant (Figure 4). The analysis of variance showed no significant difference ($p=0.591523$). Thus, all isolates had similar aggressiveness as shown in Figure 4.

* Data with the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level according to the Newman-Keuls test.

Figure 4 : Average number of axillary brooms according to isolates

4. DISCUSSION

The objective of this work was to test the pathogenicity of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates on plants and to identify the characteristics of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates on PDA and carrot media for mycelial growth. The results of this study showed that *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates can grow on both PDA and carrot medium and that there is an interaction between the culture media and the isolates. Indeed, the composition of the culture medium is an important factor for the growth and sporulation of the fungal species. Thus, isolates KOCIV 1-2 and KOCIV 1-3 grew more on the PDA medium and isolates KOCIV 1-1 and KOCIV 1-6 on the carrot medium. The growth of isolates KOCIV 1-4 and KOCIV 1-5 did not vary from one medium to another. In general, isolates KOCIV 1-6 and KOCIV 1-1 showed the highest growth rates on all media and both isolates grew faster on the carrot medium than on the PDA medium. According to Kachulire (2017), carrot is more rich in vitamin than potato. This difference in vitamin content could explain this high mycelial growth of KOCIV 1-6 and KOCIV 1-1 isolates in the carrot culture medium. Indeed, growth stimulation seems to be observed in culture media containing amino acids, vitamins and essential nutrients, which combined, significantly influence mycelial growth on these culture media. This point of view is also shared by Kadiri and Kehinde (1990) who analysed the effects of vitamins on mycelial growth in the genus *Trichoderma* and had found that all components accelerated mycelial growth. Our results are also in line with those of Kachulire (2017). In his study, he showed that the average mycelial growth rate on carrot medium was 6.63 cm/day for carrot compared to 2.5 cm/day for potato. The carrot medium could be used for different outgrowths of mycelial filaments during mycelial multiplication processes. The mycelial development of isolates on one medium compared to the other could also suggest a possible difference in isolates. The study of the pathogenicity of *Moniliophthora* spp. populations showed that all six isolates caused symptoms of witches' broom disease on the plants after seven days of inoculation for isolates KOCIV 1-1, KOCIV 1-2, KOCIV 1-3 and KOCIV 1-4 and two weeks after inoculation for isolates KOCIV 1-5 and KOCIV 1-6. The first symptoms appeared as an uncontrolled proliferation of axillary buds. The uninoculated plants (control plants) were all apparently healthy. This suggests that *Moniliophthora* spp. is the causal agent of witches' broom disease in the kola tree. The values for time to symptom onset would show a difference between isolates. The rate of diseased plants per isolate six months after inoculation varied from 33% to 59%. The variation in the rate of infected plants could be due also to the nature of the isolates. Indeed, isolate KOCIV 1-4 had the highest virulence rate and isolate KOCIV 1-6 had the lowest virulence rate. In the host-pathogen context, isolate KOCIV 1-4 would be more virulent and isolate KOCIV 1-6 would be less virulent; these isolates would therefore differ. The variation in the rate of infected plants would be due also to the nature of the plant material used. In a population of "all-comers" nuts, there is a high degree of heterogeneity among plants, both morphologically and genotypically. Based on this

hypothesis, some plants, because of their genetic uniqueness, are predisposed to show symptoms in the presence of a pathogen.

CONCLUSION ET PERSPECTIVES

The study of the pathogenicity of the *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates showed that there is pathogenic diversity within the *Moniliophthora* spp. population, resulting in several levels of virulence. The symptoms on the plants were identical to those observed on the plants used for isolation. The pathogenicity study allowed us to show that *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates are responsible for the symptoms of witches' broom disease on inoculated plants; this leads us to say that this fungus would be responsible for witches' broom disease on the kola trees. However, in order to better appreciate the variability of the virulence of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates, additional sample collections could be directed to other production areas in order to obtain a larger number of *Moniliophthora* spp. isolates. It would be also important to accurately identify the causal agent of the disease by molecular tools. In addition, the selection of resistant/tolerant kola trees would be an alternative to considerably reduce the impact of the disease on orchard productivity.

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